

MATHEMATICS

ASYMMETRIC NATURAL VIBRATIONS OF A FLUID CONTAINING CYLINDRICAL SHELL STIFFENED WITH RODS AND SUBJECTED TO THE ACTION OF COMPRESSIVE FORCE ALONG THE AXIS

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Abstract

The paper studies asymmetric natural vibrations of a fluid-filled cylindrical shell stiffened with rods subjected to the action of compressive force along the axis. Using the constructive-orthotropic model of the shell, compressive models of fluid and contact conditions, a frequency equation for the system under consideration was structured. The obtained equation is a transcendental equation with respect to the desired frequency parameter. Using the logarithmic derivative of the Bessel function, based on the shell thickness and character of change in the stress-strain of the shell, an analytic expression for the vibration frequency of the system under consideration was obtained and the influence of physical and geometrical parameters characterizing the system on these parameters was studied.

Keywords: compressive force, stiffened with rods, cylindrical shell, vibrations, stress.

The system under consideration consists of a cylindrical shell stiffened with rods and fluid completely filling its inside. Therefore, for studying vibrations of such a system, we will use equations of motion of a cylindrical shell stiffened with rods, of fluid and additional contact conditions.

Fundamentals of theory of deformation of shells stiffened with rods was given by V.Z.Vlasov [1] and A.I.Lourie [2].

Under the cylindrical shell stiffened with rods we understand a system consisting of a cylindrical shell and rods rigidly stiffened to it along the coordinate lines (Fig. 1).

It is considered that the coordinate axes coincide with principal curvature lines and rigidly contact with

the shell along these lines. Using the Ostrogradsky-Hamilton variation principle, we can derive the system of main equations of the mentioned system. It is considered that the stress-strain state of the cylindrical shell is completely determined by the equations of linear theory of shells, based on Kirchhoff-Liav conjecture. In the calculation of rods the equations based on Kirchhoff-Glebsh theory on for straight axis rods are used.

When the cylindrical shell is under the action of compressive stress σ_x along the axis, its potential energy is determined as follows [3]:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathfrak{D} = & \frac{Eh}{2(1-\nu^2)} \int_0^{\xi_1} \int_0^{2\pi} \left\{ \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial \xi} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial \theta} - w \right)^2 + 2(1-\nu) \left[\frac{\partial u}{\partial \xi} \left(\frac{\partial v}{\partial \theta} - w \right) - \right. \right. \\ & \left. \left. - \frac{1}{4} \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial \theta} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial \xi} \right)^2 \right] \right\} d\xi d\theta + \frac{Eh^3}{24(1-\nu^2)R^2} \int_0^{\xi_1} \int_0^{2\pi} \left\{ \left(\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial \xi^2} + \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial \theta^2} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial \theta} \right)^2 - \right. \\ & \left. - 2(1-\nu) \left[\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial \xi^2} \left(\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial \theta^2} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial \theta} \right) - \left(\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial \xi \partial \theta} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial \xi} \right)^2 \right] \right\} d\xi d\theta + \\ & + \frac{E_s}{2R} \sum_{j=1}^{k_1} \int_0^{2\pi} \left[F_s \left(\frac{\partial v}{\partial \theta} - w - \frac{h_s}{R} \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial \theta^2} \right)^2 + \frac{I_{xs}}{R^2} \left(\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial \theta^2} + w \right)^2 + \frac{G_s}{R^2 E_s} I_{kp.s} \times \right. \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

Fig. 1. A medium-contacting cylindrical shell stiffened with rods subjected to the action of compressive force.

$$\begin{aligned} & \times \left(\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial \xi \partial \theta} + \frac{\partial u}{\partial \theta} \right)^2 \Bigg]_{\xi=\xi_j} d\theta - \frac{\sigma_x h}{2} \int_0^{\xi_1} \int_0^{2\pi} \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial \xi} \right)^2 d\xi d\theta - \frac{\sigma_x F_c}{2R} \sum_{i=1}^k \int_0^{\xi_1} \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial \xi} \right)^2 \Bigg|_{\theta=\theta_i} d\xi + \\ & + \frac{E_c}{2R} \sum_{i=1}^{k_2} \int_0^{\xi_1} \left[F_c \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial \xi} - \frac{h_c}{R} \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial \xi^2} \right)^2 + \frac{I_{yc}}{R^2} \left(\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial \xi^2} \right)^2 + \frac{G_c}{E_c} I_{kp.c} \left(\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial \xi \partial \theta} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial \xi} \right)^2 \right] \Bigg|_{\theta=\theta_i} d\xi. \end{aligned}$$

In the expressions u, v, w are displacements of the shell, E, ν – are elasticity modulus and the Poisson ratio of the cylindrical shell, respectively, R, h are radii and thickness of the cylindrical shell, respectively, E_c, E_s are elasticity module of the longitudinal rod and ring, respectively, F_c, F_s are cross-section areas of the longitudinal rod and ring, respectively, $I_{yc}, I_{kp.c}$ are inertia moments of the cross section of the longitudinal rod, respectively, $I_{xy}, I_{kp.s}$ are inertia moments of the cross-section of the ring, q_x, q_θ, q_r are the components of stress force acting on the cylindrical shell as viewed from medium, G_c, G_s are elasticity module in shear of the longitudinal rod and ring.

The kinetic energy of the shell stiffened with rods is as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
K = & \frac{Eh}{2(1-\nu^2)} \int_0^{\xi_1} \int_0^{2\pi} \left[\left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial t_1} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial v}{\partial t_1} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial t_1} \right)^2 \right] d\xi d\theta + \\
& + \frac{\bar{\rho}_c E_c F_c}{2R(1-\nu^2)} \sum_{i=1}^{k_2} \int_0^{\xi_1} \left[\left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial t_1} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial t_1} \right)^2 \right]_{\theta=\theta_j} d\xi + \\
& + \frac{\bar{\rho}_s E_s F_s}{2R(1-\nu^2)} \sum_{i=1}^{k_1} \int_0^{2\pi} \left[\left(\frac{\partial v}{\partial t_1} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial t_1} \right)^2 \right]_{\xi=\xi_j} d\theta \quad (2)
\end{aligned}$$

Using the Ostrogradsky-Hamilton condition of stationarity of action, we can obtain the equation of motion of a shell stiffened with rods:

$$\delta W = \delta(\mathcal{E} + K) = 0 \quad (3)$$

Here $W = \int_{t_0}^{t_1} \tilde{L} dt$ is Hamilton's action, $\tilde{L} = K - \Pi$ is a Lagrange function. Carrying out the varia-

tion operation and taking into account that the variations δu , δv , δw are arbitrary and independent, we obtain the following system of equations of motion:

$$\begin{cases}
L_x(u, v, w) + q_x = 0 \\
L_y(u, v, w) + q_y = 0 \\
L_z(u, v, w) - (q_z - q_{zz}) = 0
\end{cases} \quad (4)$$

Hence we obtain the system of equations of motion of a constructive orthotropic cylindrical shell in displacements:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left[\left(1 + \gamma_c^{(1)} \right) \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \xi^2} + \frac{1-\nu}{2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \theta^2} \right] u + \frac{1+\nu}{2} \frac{\partial^2 \mathcal{G}}{\partial \xi \partial \theta} - \left(\nu \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi} + \delta_c^{(1)} \frac{\partial^3}{\partial \xi^3} \right) w - \rho_1 \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial t_1^2} = \\
& = - \frac{R^2 (1-\nu^2)}{Eh} q_x, \\
& \frac{1+\nu}{2} \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial \xi \partial \theta} + \left\{ \frac{1-\nu}{2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \xi^2} + \left[1 + \left(1 - \frac{h_s}{R} \right)^2 \gamma_s^{(2)} \right] \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \theta^2} \right\} \mathcal{G} + \\
& + \left\{ - \left[1 + \left(1 - \frac{h_s}{R} \right) \gamma_s^{(2)} \right] \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} + (2-\nu) a^2 \frac{\partial^3}{\partial \xi^2 \partial \theta} + \left[a^2 - \left(1 - \frac{h_s}{R} \right) \delta_s^{(2)} \right] \frac{\partial^3}{\partial \theta^3} \right\} w - \rho_2 \frac{\partial^2 \mathcal{G}}{\partial t_1^2} = \\
& = - \frac{R^2 (1-\nu^2)}{Eh} q_y \quad (5)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& - \left(\nu \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi} + \delta_c^{(1)} \frac{\partial^3}{\partial \xi^3} \right) u + \left\{ - \left[1 + \left(1 - \frac{h_s}{R} \right) \gamma_s^{(2)} \right] \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} + (2 - \nu) a^2 \frac{\partial^3}{\partial \xi^2 \partial \theta} + \right. \\
& \left. + \left[a^2 - \left(1 - \frac{h_s}{R} \right) \delta_s^{(2)} \right] \frac{\partial^3}{\partial \theta^3} \right\} v + \left[1 + \gamma_s^{(2)} + \eta_{s1}^{(2)} + 2 \left(\delta_s^{(2)} + \eta_{s1}^{(2)} \right) \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \theta^2} + a^2 \Delta \Delta + \right. \\
& \left. + \left(\eta_{s1}^{(2)} + \eta_{s2}^{(2)} \right) \frac{\partial^4}{\partial \theta^4} + \eta_c^{(1)} \frac{\partial^4}{\partial \xi^4} + \bar{p} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \xi^2} \right] w + \rho_3 \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial t_1^2} = \frac{R^2 (1 - \nu^2)}{Eh} q_z
\end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Here } \rho_1 = 1 + \bar{\rho}_c \bar{\gamma}_c^{(1)}, \rho_2 = 1 + \bar{\rho}_s \bar{\gamma}_s^{(2)}, \rho_3 = 1 + \bar{\rho}_c \bar{\gamma}_c^{(1)} + \bar{\rho}_s \bar{\gamma}_s^{(2)},$$

The above system of equations and the constants contained in the expressions are expressed by the geometrical, physical mechanical parameters of cylindrical shells as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
a^2 &= \frac{h^2}{12R^2}, \bar{\rho}_s = \frac{\rho_s}{\rho_0}, \bar{\rho}_c = \frac{\rho_c}{\rho_0}, \Delta = \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \xi^2} + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \theta^2}, L_1 = x_2 - x_1 \\
\bar{\gamma}_s^{(1)} &= \frac{F_s}{Lh}, \bar{\delta}_s^{(1)} = \frac{h_s}{R} \bar{\gamma}_s^{(1)}, \eta_{s2}^{(1)} = \left(\frac{h_s}{R} \right)^2, \bar{\mu}_s^1 = \frac{J_{kps}}{LhR^2}, \gamma_s^{(1)} = \frac{E_s (1 - \nu^2)}{E} \bar{\eta}_s^1, \\
\delta_s^{(1)} &= \frac{h_s}{R} \bar{\gamma}_s^{(1)}, \eta_{s2}^{(1)} = \frac{E_s (1 - \nu^2)}{E} \eta_{s2}^{(1)}, \bar{\eta}_{s2}^1 = \frac{E_s J_{xs} (1 - \nu^2)}{ELhR^2}, \gamma_c^{(1)} = \frac{E_c}{E} (1 - \nu^2) \bar{\gamma}_c^{(1)}, \\
\lambda_{1h}^{(1)} &= \frac{E_s J_{zs} (1 - \nu^2)}{ELhR^2}, \lambda_{2s}^{(1)} = \frac{h_s}{R} \lambda_{1s}^{(1)}, \lambda_{3s}^{(1)} = \left(\frac{h_s}{R} \right)^2 \lambda_{1s}^{(1)}, \mu_s^{(1)} = \frac{G_s}{E} (1 - \nu^2) \bar{\mu}_s^{(1)}, \\
\delta_1(\xi - \xi_1) &= L \delta(x - x_1), \delta_1(\xi - \xi_j) = \frac{L_1}{k_1 + 1} \delta(x - x_j), \xi = \frac{x}{R}, \\
\bar{\gamma}_c^{(1)} &= \frac{E_c k}{2\pi R h}, \delta_c^{(1)} = \frac{h_c}{R} \bar{\gamma}_c^{(1)}, \theta = \frac{y}{R}, t_1 = \omega_0 t, \omega_0 = \sqrt{\frac{E}{(1 - \nu^2) \rho_0 R^2}}. \\
\eta_c^{(1)} &= \frac{E_c (J_{yc} + h^2 F_c) k_1}{2\pi R^3 h E} (1 - \nu^2). \tag{6}
\end{aligned}$$

Propagation of small perturbations in ideal fluid is expressed by the following equation [4]:

$$\nabla^2 \Phi - \frac{1}{a^2} \frac{\partial^2 \Phi}{\partial t^2} = 0. \tag{7}$$

Here Φ is fluid's potential, a is speed of sound propagation in fluid. In the case of harmonic vibration the equation (7) goes into the Helmholtz equation:

$$\nabla^2 \Phi + \frac{\omega^2}{a^2} \Phi = 0. \tag{8}$$

When fluid is incompressible, as $a^2 \rightarrow \infty$ the equation (8) goes into the Laplace equation:

$$\nabla^2 \Phi = 0. \tag{9}$$

If fluid is an ideal fluid with two-phase bubbles, in this fluid the propagation of small perturbations is determined by the following equality [2]:

$$\frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial x^2} - \frac{1}{a^2} \frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial t^2} - \frac{2\rho_{jo} R}{Eh} \frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial t^2} = 0. \tag{10}$$

Here $a^2 = \frac{1}{\alpha_{20}(1-\alpha_{20})} \left(\frac{\rho_{10}}{\rho_{10} - \rho_{20}} \right) \frac{p_0}{p_{10}^0}$, ρ_{10}, ρ_{20} is real density of fluid and gas; p_0 is static

pressure; ρ_{j_0} - is density of the mixture; α_{20} is the volume of gas bubbles;

The zero index corresponds to the values of parameters in the equilibrium case

$$\rho_{j_0} = (1 - \alpha_{20})\rho_{10} + \alpha_{20}\rho_{20}.$$

To the system of equations of motion (5) we add the equations of motion of fluid (7) the contact conditions to (10).

The equality of tangential stresses to zero is taken as equality of normal components speed and pressure on the contact surface of fluid and shell:

$$\mathcal{G}_r = \frac{\partial w}{\partial t}, \quad q_z = -p, \quad q_x = q_y = 0 \quad (r = R) \quad (11)$$

Here q_x, q_y, q_z are the components of pressure force on the shell as viewed from fluid.

The systems of equations of motion of the shell stiffened with rods and of fluid (7)-(10) together with contact conditions (11) enable to solve a problem on free vibrations of the system a constructive-orthotropic shell - fluid.

In other words, the study of free vibrations of a medium and fluid contacting orthotropic cylindrical shell is reduced to joint integration of the system of the equations of a constructive-orthotropic shell and equations of motion of fluid within contact conditions. Assume that a cylindrical shell subjected to the action of compressive force along the axis and with fluid-filled interior domain was stiffened only with longitudinal rods. Let us study its asymmetric natural vibrations. Taking in the system of equation (5) the "c" indexed quantities equal to zero, we obtain the system of equations of motion of a cylindrical shell subjected to the action of compressive force along the axis and with fluid-filled interior domain in displacements:

$$\begin{aligned} & \left[(1 + \bar{\gamma}_c^{(1)}) \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \xi^2} + \frac{1 - \nu}{2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \theta^2} \right] u + \frac{1 + \nu}{2} \frac{\partial^2 \mathcal{G}}{\partial \xi \partial \theta} - \left(\nu \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi} + \delta_c^{(1)} \frac{\partial^3}{\partial \xi^3} \right) w - \rho_1 \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial t_1^2} = 0 \\ & \frac{1 + \nu}{2} \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial \xi \partial \theta} + \left[\frac{1 - \nu}{2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \xi^2} + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \theta^2} \right] \mathcal{G} - \frac{\partial w}{\partial \theta} - \rho_2 \frac{\partial^2 \mathcal{G}}{\partial t_1^2} = 0, \quad (12) \\ & - \left(\nu \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi} + \delta_c^{(1)} \frac{\partial^3}{\partial \xi^3} \right) u - \frac{\partial v}{\partial \theta} + \left[1 + a^2 \Delta \Delta + \eta_c^{(1)} \frac{\partial^4}{\partial \xi^4} + \bar{p} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \xi^2} \right] w + \rho_3 \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial t_1^2} = \frac{R^2 (1 - \nu^2)}{Eh} q_z \end{aligned}$$

At first let us find the pressure force on a cylindrical shell as viewed from fluid. We look for the potential Φ contained in equation (8) in the following from:

$$\Phi = R(r) \sin kx \cos \omega t \quad (13)$$

Writing this expression in the equation (8) written in the cylindrical coordinates system we obtain:

$$\frac{d^2 R(r)}{dr^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{dR(r)}{dr} + \left(\gamma^2 - \frac{n^2}{r^2} \right) R(r) = 0 \quad (14)$$

Here

$$\gamma^2 = k^2 - \frac{\omega^2}{a^2}$$

The general solution of the equation (14) can be written by means of two Bessel functions as follows:

$$R(r) = A_n Z_n^{(1)}(\gamma r) + B_n Z_n^{(2)}(\gamma r). \quad (15)$$

The form of the function $Z_n(\gamma r)$ depends on the values of the parameter γ . This parameter itself is a multi-valued function of k . Write the parameter γ in the following form:

$$\gamma = \begin{cases} \sqrt{\left(\frac{\omega}{a} - k\right)\left(\frac{\omega}{a} + k\right)}, & \frac{\omega}{a} > k \\ i \sqrt{\left(k - \frac{\omega}{a}\right)\left(k + \frac{\omega}{a}\right)} = i\tilde{\gamma}, & \frac{\omega}{a} < k \end{cases}$$

For $\gamma = i\tilde{\gamma}$ (14) takes the form:

$$\frac{d^2 R(r)}{dr^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{dR(r)}{dr} - \left(\tilde{\gamma}^2 + \frac{n^2}{r^2}\right) R(r) = 0$$

The solutions of the last equation are the Bessel functions $I_n(\tilde{\gamma}r)$ and $K_n(\tilde{\gamma}r)$. Since fluid fills the interior of the cylindrical shell, the point $p=0$ enters the domain of solution of the problem. As this point, since the function $K_n(\tilde{\gamma}r)$ is unbounded the solution of the Bessel equation is in the form:

$$\Phi = A_n I_n(\tilde{\gamma}r) \sin kx \sin n\varphi \cos \omega t. \quad (16)$$

When the expression of the potential Φ is known, we can determine the pressure P of fluid and the radial velocity $\mathcal{G}_r$ of its points:

$$P = -\rho_0 \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial t}; \quad \mathcal{G}_r = \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial r} \quad (17)$$

Using the expressions (16) and (17) we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} P &= A_n \rho_0 \omega I_n(\tilde{\gamma}r) \sin kx \cos n\varphi \sin \omega t \\ \mathcal{G}_r &= A_n \tilde{\gamma} I_n'(\tilde{\gamma}r) \sin kx \cos n\varphi \cos \omega t \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

We will look for the solution of the system of equations of motion of the shell (4) in displacements in the following form:

$$\begin{aligned} u &= A \cos n\varphi \cos kx \sin \omega t \\ v &= B \sin n\varphi \sin kx \sin \omega t \\ w &= C \cos n\varphi \sin kx \sin \omega t \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

Here A,B,C (are constants, n is the number of waves in circular direction, π/k is the number of half-waves along the generatrix of the cylinder, ω is circular frequency.

Using the first one of the expressions of (11), the solutions (18) and (19) we can express the constant A_n by C;

$$A_n = \frac{\omega}{\tilde{\gamma} I_n'(\tilde{\gamma}R)} C$$

Substituting this expression of A_n in the first of (18) we obtain;

$$P = \frac{\rho_0 \omega^2 I_n(\tilde{\gamma}r)}{\tilde{\gamma} I_n'(\tilde{\gamma}R)} C \sin kx \cos n\varphi \sin \omega t.$$

In this equality, writing $r = R$ for the value of pressure in the contact we obtain:

$$P = \frac{\rho_0 \omega^2 I_n(\tilde{\gamma}R)}{\tilde{\gamma} I_n'(\tilde{\gamma}R)} C \sin kx \cos n\varphi \sin \omega t. \quad (20)$$

Using the system of equations of motion of the cylinder (12) and their solutions (19), the expression (20) of pressure on the cylindrical shell as viewed from fluid, with respect to the constants A, B, C we obtain a system of homogeneous linear equations

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left[-\left(1 + \gamma_c^{(1)}\right) \chi^2 - \frac{1-\nu}{2} n^2 + \rho_1 \omega_1^2 \right] A - \frac{1+\nu}{2} \chi n B + \left(\nu \chi + \delta_c^{(1)} \chi^3 \right) C = 0 \\
& -\frac{1+\nu}{2} \chi n A + \left[-\frac{1+\nu}{2} (1+4a^2) \chi^2 - (1+a^2) n^2 + \rho_2 \omega_1^2 \right] B + \\
& + \left(n + (2-\nu) a^2 \chi^2 n + a^2 n^3 \right) C = 0 \tag{21} \\
& \left(-\nu \chi + \delta_c^{(1)} \chi^3 \right) A + \left(-n - (2-\nu) a^2 \chi^2 n + a^2 n^3 \right) B + \\
& + \left[1 + a^2 (n^2 + \chi^2)^2 + \eta_c^{(1)} \chi^4 - \chi^2 \bar{p} - \rho_3 \omega_1^2 - \frac{\omega_1^2 \rho J_n(\gamma R)}{\rho_0 h \gamma J'_n(\gamma R)} \right] C = 0
\end{aligned}$$

We write the system (21) in the following form:

$$a_{i1} A + a_{i2} B + a_{i3} C = 0 \quad (i=1,2,3), \tag{22}$$

Here

$$\begin{aligned}
a_{11} &= -\left(1 + \gamma_c^{(1)}\right) \chi^2 - \frac{1-\nu}{2} n^2 + \rho_1 \omega_1^2 = \tilde{a}_{11} + \rho_1 \omega_1^2; \quad a_{12} = -\frac{1+\nu}{2} \chi n; \\
a_{13} &= \nu \chi + \delta_c^{(1)} \chi^3; \quad a_{21} = -\frac{1+\nu}{2} \chi n; \quad a_{22} = -\frac{1+\nu}{2} (1+4a^2) \chi^2 - \\
& -\left(1 + a^2\right) n^2 + \rho_2 \omega_1^2 = \tilde{a}_{22} + \rho_2 \omega_1^2; \quad a_{23} = n + (2-\nu) a^2 \chi^2 n + a^2 n^3; \\
a_{31} &= -\nu \chi + \delta_c^{(1)} \chi^3; \quad a_{32} = -n - (2-\nu) a^2 \chi^2 n + a^2 n^3; \\
a_{33} &= 1 + a^2 (n^2 + \chi^2)^2 + \eta_c^{(1)} \chi^4 - \chi^2 \bar{p} - \rho_3 \omega_1^2 - \frac{\omega_1^2 \rho J_n(\gamma R)}{\rho_0 h \gamma J'_n(\gamma R)} = \tilde{a}_{33} - \rho_1 \omega_1^2 - \chi^2 \bar{p}.
\end{aligned}$$

The system (22) is a system of homogeneous linear equations with respect to the constants $A, B, C, \tilde{A}_s, \tilde{B}_s, \tilde{C}_s$. The necessary and sufficient condition for the existence of its non-zero solution is the equality of its principal determinant to zero:

$$\det \|a_{ij}\| = 0, \quad (i, j = 1, 2, 3) \tag{23}$$

Since desired ω_1 parameter of the frequency equation (23) it is included into the argument of the Bessel function J_n , is transcendental.

Let us write the equation (23) as follows:

$$\begin{vmatrix}
\tilde{a}_{11} + \rho_1 \omega_1^2 & a_{12} & a_{13} \\
a_{21} & \tilde{a}_{22} + \rho_2 \omega_1^2 & a_{23} \\
a_{31} & a_{32} & \tilde{a}_{33} - \rho_1 \omega_1^2 - \chi^2 \bar{p}
\end{vmatrix} = 0. \tag{24}$$

We can write this equation with respect to $\omega_1^2 = \lambda$ as follows:

$$a_1(\lambda) \lambda^3 + a_2(\lambda) \lambda^2 + a_3(\lambda) \lambda + a_4(\lambda) = 0 \tag{25}$$

$a_i(\lambda)$ ($i=1,2,\dots,4$) is in the following form:

$$a_1(\lambda) = \rho_1 \rho_1; \quad a_2(\lambda) = \rho_1 (\tilde{a}_{11} + \rho_1 \tilde{a}_{22}) - \rho_1 (\tilde{a}_{33} - \chi^2 \bar{p}); \tag{26}$$

$$a_3(\lambda) = -(\tilde{a}_{33} - \chi^2 \bar{p})(\tilde{a}_{11} + \rho_1 \tilde{a}_{22}) + \varphi_1 \tilde{a}_{11} \tilde{a}_{22} + a_{13} a_{31} + \rho_1 a_{32} a_{23} - \varphi_1 a_{21} a_{12};$$

$$a_4(\lambda) = (\tilde{a}_{33} - \chi^2 \bar{p})(a_{21} a_{12} - \tilde{a}_{11} \tilde{a}_{22}) - a_{21} a_{32} a_{13} - a_{12} a_{23} a_{31} + a_{31} a_{13} \tilde{a}_{22} + a_{32} a_{23} \tilde{a}_{11}.$$

For finding approximate roots of the equation (25), at first we simplify its coefficients. The studies show that the coefficients a_i ($i = 1, \dots, 4$) mainly sharply vary depending on the parameters $\eta_c^{(1)}, a^2, n, \delta_c^{(1)}$. It should be noted that in the problems studying the vibrations of cylindrical shells, it suffices to retain the terms with highest rate of change. Analysis of parameters included in the coefficients of the equation (25) shows that it can be simplified only when longitudinal waves are formed in the cylindrical shell. If as a unit of measure we accept the relative thickness $a = \frac{h}{\sqrt{12R}}$, we can show the parameters $\eta_c^{(1)}, a^2, n, \delta_c^{(1)}, q_z^{(0)}$ as a powers of a – as follows:

$$\eta_c^{(1)} = a^\beta, \quad \delta_c^{(1)} = a^{\beta/2}, \quad n = a^{-\mu}, \quad \bar{p} = a^{\beta_1}, \quad q_z^{(0)} = a^{\beta_2}. \quad (27)$$

Here $\beta, \mu, \beta_1, \beta_2$ are positive numbers. Taking into account the validity of the inequality $\delta_c^1 \leq \sqrt{\eta_c^1}$, when studying the order of the coefficients $a_i(\lambda)$ we will take $\delta_c^1 \approx \sqrt{\eta_c^1}$.

Furthermore, we will analyze the equation (25) in the domain of small frequencies. Then for rather large n ($x \ll n$) we will use the following logarithmic derivative of the Bessel function J_n :

$$\frac{J'_n(x)}{J_n(x)} \approx \frac{n}{x} - \frac{x}{2n} \quad (28)$$

Note that when fluid is incompressible, it suffices to retain only one term in the right hand side of the expression (28). In this case the relative error will be of order $O((x/n)^2)$. Taking into account what has been said, we can reduce the equation (25) to the following algebraic equation:

$$\tilde{a}_1 \lambda^3 + \tilde{a}_2 \lambda^2 + \tilde{a}_3 \lambda + \tilde{a}_4 = 0 \quad (29)$$

Here

$$\tilde{a}_1 = \frac{\rho^* \rho_1}{nh^*}, \quad \tilde{a}_2 = \frac{\rho^*}{nh^*} (\tilde{a}_{11} + \rho_1 \tilde{a}_{22}) - \rho_1 (\tilde{a}_{33} - \chi^2 \bar{p});$$

$$\tilde{a}_3 = -(\tilde{a}_{33} - \chi^2 \bar{p})(\tilde{a}_{11} + \rho_1 \tilde{a}_{22}) + \frac{\rho^*}{nh^*} (\tilde{a}_{11} \tilde{a}_{22} - a_{21} a_{12}) + a_{13} a_{31} + \rho_1 a_{32} a_{23};$$

$$\tilde{a}_4 = (\tilde{a}_{33} - \chi^2 \bar{p})(a_{21} a_{12} - \tilde{a}_{11} \tilde{a}_{22}) - a_{21} a_{32} a_{13} - a_{12} a_{23} a_{31} + a_{31} a_{13} \tilde{a}_{22} + a_{32} a_{23} \tilde{a}_{11}.$$

For finding the small root of the equation (29) in the domain of small frequencies, we can remove the terms contained in λ^2 and λ^3 . As a result, we get:

$$\lambda = \frac{(\tilde{a}_{33} - \chi^2 \bar{p})(\tilde{a}_{21} a_{12} + \tilde{a}_{11} \tilde{a}_{22}) - a_{21} a_{32} a_{13} - a_{12} a_{23} a_{31} + a_{31} a_{13} \tilde{a}_{22} + a_{32} a_{23} \tilde{a}_{11}}{(\tilde{a}_{33} - \chi^2 \bar{p})(\tilde{a}_{11} + \rho_1 \tilde{a}_{22}) + \frac{\rho^*}{nh^*} (\tilde{a}_{11} \tilde{a}_{22} - a_{21} a_{12}) - a_{13} a_{31} - \rho_1 a_{32} a_{23}} \quad (30)$$

By means of the formula (30) we can calculate small frequencies of a cylindrical shell subjected to the action of compressive force along the axis and whose interior domain is filled with incompressible fluid and stiffened only with longitudinal rods.

When fluid is compressible, in the right side of the expression (28) we must retain both addends. In this case we obtain:

$$\tilde{a}_{10} \lambda^4 + \tilde{a}_{11} \lambda^3 + \tilde{a}_{12} \lambda^2 + \tilde{a}_{13} \lambda + \tilde{a}_{14} = 0 \quad (31)$$

As a result, we obtain:

$$\lambda_{sx} = \frac{\sqrt{\tilde{a}_{13}^2 - 4\tilde{a}_{12}\tilde{a}_{14}} - \tilde{a}_{13}}{2\tilde{a}_{12}} \quad (32)$$

By means of the expressions (30) and (32) we can relate small frequencies of a cylindrical shell subjected to the action of the compressive force whose interior domain is filled with compressible and incompressible fluid and stiffened only with longitudinal rods:

$$\lambda_{sx} = \lambda(1 - \psi); \quad \psi = \frac{\sqrt{\tilde{a}_{13}^4 - 4\tilde{a}_{12}\tilde{a}_{14}\tilde{a}_{13}^2} - \tilde{a}_{13}^2}{2\tilde{a}_{12}\tilde{a}_{14}}$$

As can be seen from the last expression, taking into account the compression ratio of fluid frequencies of a cylindrical shell subjected to the action of compressive forces along the axis and longitudinally stiffened only with rods are smaller compared to the frequencies of a cylindrical shell subjected to the action of compressive force stiffened only with longitudinal rods when fluid is incompressible.

The rods of the equation (25) were found by the numerical method. The following values were taken for physical and mechanical parameters characterizing the system:

$$E = E_c = 6,67 \cdot 10^9 \text{ N/m}^2; \nu = 0,3; \chi = 1; n = 8; h_c = 1,39 \text{ mm}; R = 160 \text{ mm};$$

$$L_1 = 800 \text{ mm}; \frac{F_c}{2\pi R h} = 0,1591 \cdot 10^{-1}; \frac{I_{yc}}{2\pi R^3 h} = 0,8289 \cdot 10^{-6}; h = 0,45 \text{ mm}; k = 4;$$

$$\frac{I_{kp.c}}{2\pi R^3 h} = 0,5305 \cdot 10^{-6}; |h_c| = 0,1375 \cdot 10^{-1} R; \rho_0 = \rho_c = 7,8 \text{ q/sm}^3; \rho = 1 \text{ q/sm}^3.$$

The results of calculations were given in fig 2 and 3 in the form of dependence of ω_1 — on the wave number n — and compressive force σ_x — in the circular direction. In Figure 2, the dashed lines correspond to compressive cases, entire lines to the incompressible cases of fluid.

As can be seen from the figure, small frequencies of a cylindrical shell subjected to the action of compressive forces along the axis and longitudinally stiffened only with rods are smaller compared to the frequencies of a cylindrical shell subjected to the action of compressive force, stiffened only with longitudinal rods when fluid is incompressible.

Figure 1.3. shows that in certain limits of compressive force its influence of frequencies of a fluid-filled cylindrical shell stiffened only with longitudinal rods can be ignored. But after some limits, it sharply decreases the frequencies of the system to zero.

Fig. 2. Dependence of the frequency ω_1 on the wave number n in the direction of circular coordinate axis.

Fig. 3. Dependence of the frequency ω_1 on the compressive force σ_x .

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